

Thermal influence on cast iron corrosion in aqueous salt solutions and composite water

Rita Mehra* and Aditi Soni

Department of Pure and Applied Chemistry, Maharshi Dayanand Saraswati University, Ajmer-305 009, India

Fax : 91-0145-441176/443376

Manuscript received 4 February 2002, revised 24 June 2002, accepted 13 August 2002

The corrosion behavior of cast iron in aqueous salt solutions and in composite water at various thermal conditions has been studied by weight-loss, open-circuit potential and potentiostatic methods. The corrosion rate of cast iron increases and the open-circuit potential shifts towards less noble direction with increase of temperature. Cast iron corrosion is higher in aqueous solution of NaCl and KCl salt than other salts. The cathodic and anodic polarization curves exhibit that the reaction is controlled cathodically.

Various studies¹ have been carried out for determination of corrosion behavior of cast iron in aqueous solutions and in water. The corrosion of cast iron in water is mainly due to dissolved salts and oxygen. It is important to assess the corrosion behavior of ions present in water, the extent to

which they contribute to corrosion in water as well as the limiting values in percentage to which corrosion rate should be minimized in order to provide excellent corrosion resistance². Hence the title investigation was undertaken.

Table 1. Effect of temperature on weight-loss of cast iron at various temperature in various aqueous salts solutions and in composite water for 24 h period of immersion

Solution	Weight-loss (mg)/(dm ²) ± S.D. at							Rel. in	%Co ntri.	E _a kJ mol ⁻¹
	20°	35°	45°	55°	65°	75°	80°			
NaCl (A)	15.416 ±1.72	20.499 ±2.08	24.083 ±1.18	28.416 ±2.10	33.499 ±1.98	39.666 ±2.47	42.749 ±3.02	2.562	24.38	21.93
KCl (B)	14.916 ±0.44	19.416 ±0.50	22.999 ±1.22	26.916 ±1.18	32.499 ±2.04	38.499 ±2.30	40.499 ±2.62	2.436	22.77	22.25
Na ₂ SO ₄ (C)	6.499 ±0.28	9.749 ±0.23	12.333 ±0.65	14.999 ±0.32	17.000 ±0.86	21.416 ±1.20	24.166 ±1.27	4.218	12.34	22.76
CaCO ₃ (D)	6.416 ±0.18	8.166 ±0.23	10.749 ±0.55	13.499 ±0.48	16.999 ±0.96	19.500 ±0.70	20.416 ±1.10	3.572	10.57	24.12
CaCl ₂ (E)	2.916 ±0.05	4.249 ±0.07	5.499 ±0.06	6.749 ±0.08	8.333 ±0.12	10.333 ±0.70	13.416 ±0.65	4.571	5.84	25.12
MgSO ₄ (F)	3.083 ±0.02	4.75 ±0.04	6.333 ±0.04	7.749 ±0.20	8.916 ±0.44	9.750 ±0.28	10.750 ±0.96	3.080	5.17	23.42
NaHCO ₃ (G)	5.916 ±0.28	9.250 ±0.32	11.749 ±0.36	14.916 ±0.47	16.580 ±0.50	17.000 ±0.41	19.916 ±1.20	3.242	10.96	24.97
KBr (H)	0.083 ±0.00	1.583 ±0.02	2.083 ±0.06	2.499 ±0.04	3.083 ±0.02	3.916 ±0.07	4.249 ±0.06	1.422	1.96	25.82
KI (I)	0.083 ±0.01	1.666 ±0.00	2.083 ±0.03	2.666 ±0.04	3.249 ±0.08	3.999 ±0.06	4.333 ±0.06	1.200	1.96	26.51
Ph(NO ₃) ₂ (J)	0.000 ±0.00	0.000 ±0.00	0.000 ±0.00	0.083 ±0.00	1.247 ±0.04	1.581 ±0.07	1.747 ±0.05	0.778	0.71	27.11
MnSO ₄ (K)	0.000 ±0.00	0.000 ±0.00	0.000 ±0.00	0.083 ±0.00	0.166 ±0.00	1.416 ±0.02	1.500 ±0.02	0.468	0.35	27.34
NaNO ₃ (L)	1.249 ±0.01	1.999 ±0.04	2.666 ±0.02	3.333 ±0.02	4.249 ±0.04	5.499 ±0.05	5.749 ±0.07	0.469	2.83	25.02
C W	67.416 ±2.66	80.333 ±2.84	89.166 ±3.22	98.416 ±4.50	108.25 ±3.86	118.333 ±4.71	123.416 ±6.23	1.146	-	8.68

Table 2. Potentiostatic parameters for cast iron in various aqueous salts solutions and in composite water at various temperatures for 24 h period of immersion

Temp. °C	OCP -mV	E_{corr} -mV	Tafel slopes mV/dec		Tafel const.	$\log I_{corr_2}$ $\mu A\ cm^{-2}$	I_{corr_2} $\mu A\ cm^{-2}$	Corr. rate mpy	R_p
			β_a	β_c					
NaCl (A)									
20	510	460	88	135	23.16	0.99	9.77	4.935	2.36
35	514	480	74	127	20.32	1.16	14.45	7.299	1.40
45	560	525	60	115	17.14	1.25	17.78	8.982	0.96
55	612	580	45	107	13.77	1.34	21.88	11.053	0.62
65	670	640	42	85	12.22	1.40	25.12	12.689	0.48
75	686	620	37	80	10.99	1.54	34.67	17.513	0.31
80	690	650	33	80	10.16	1.56	36.31	18.342	0.27
KCl (B)									
20	505	450	102	135	25.26	0.96	9.12	4.607	2.76
35	525	475	80	130	21.53	1.12	13.18	6.658	1.63
45	552	520	67	122	18.80	1.21	16.22	8.193	1.15
55	570	540	52	116	15.61	1.30	19.95	10.078	0.78
65	587	570	50	97	14.34	1.39	24.55	12.401	0.58
75	610	590	44	95	11.88	1.45	28.18	14.235	0.42
80	663	620	40	95	12.24	1.53	33.88	17.114	0.36
Na ₂ SO ₄ (C)									
20	418	400	101	140	25.51	0.60	3.98	2.010	6.40
35	500	470	92	132	23.57	0.78	6.03	3.046	3.91
45	530	500	80	125	22.39	0.98	9.55	4.824	2.34
55	545	510	78	120	20.55	1.04	10.96	5.036	1.87
65	562	540	71	118	19.27	1.10	12.59	5.359	1.53
75	604	560	60	114	17.09	1.21	16.22	8.193	1.05
80	640	600	56	98	15.49	1.30	19.95	10.078	0.77
CaCO ₃ (D)									
20	390	370	108	155	27.67	0.43	2.69	1.359	10.28
35	404	375	98	148	25.63	0.48	3.02	1.526	8.48
45	430	420	94	144	24.72	0.58	3.80	1.919	6.50
55	455	450	95	138	22.86	0.66	4.57	2.308	5.00
65	468	452	80	138	22.01	0.66	4.57	2.308	4.81
75	432	430	90	140	23.82	0.60	3.98	2.010	5.98
80	420	400	92	144	24.41	0.58	3.80	1.919	6.41
CaCl ₂ (E)									
20	330	320	125	159	30.42	0.46	2.88	1.455	10.5
35	340	338	138	155	31.74	0.61	4.07	2.056	7.79
45	356	345	126	152	29.95	0.69	4.89	2.470	6.11
55	367	350	114	150	28.16	0.80	6.31	3.187	4.46
65	380	364	102	144	25.95	0.90	7.94	4.012	3.27
75	404	370	92	144	24.40	0.98	9.55	4.824	2.55
80	420	410	82	140	22.48	1.07	11.75	5.935	1.91
MgSO ₄ (F)									
20	335	330	120	150	28.98	0.43	2.69	1.359	10.16
35	345	340	111	145	27.34	0.61	4.07	2.056	6.75
45	358	350	102	143	25.38	0.73	5.37	2.713	4.02
55	370	354	98	140	25.06	0.82	6.61	3.338	3.79
65	382	370	95	136	24.31	0.96	9.12	4.607	2.66
75	414	380	90	134	24.70	0.96	9.12	4.607	2.71
80	420	400	88	130	22.81	0.99	9.77	4.935	2.33
NaHCO ₃ (G)									
20	392	380	114	150	28.16	0.52	3.31	1.672	8.51
35	410	390	108	150	27.30	0.65	4.47	2.258	6.11
45	425	410	100	148	25.94	0.76	5.75	2.904	4.51
55	440	450	90	136	23.54	0.87	6.92	3.496	3.40
65	440	460	86	124	22.07	0.97	9.33	4.713	2.36
75	480	470	85	118	21.48	1.07	11.75	5.935	1.83
80	484	475	80	116	20.53	1.17	14.79	7.471	1.39
KBr (H)									
20	256	250	160	193	39.03	0.08	1.20	0.686	32.52
35	275	270	160	190	37.76	0.09	1.23	0.621	30.69
45	282	280	157	186	37.01	0.11	1.29	0.652	28.69
55	305	300	152	180	35.83	0.12	1.32	0.667	27.14
65	324	315	150	174	35.02	0.20	1.58	0.798	22.16
75	351	340	148	170	34.39	0.24	1.74	0.879	19.76
80	384	380	142	166	32.65	0.31	2.04	1.030	16.00

Table-2. (contd.)

	KI (I)								
20	256	250	168	192	38.95	0.08	1.20	0.686	32.46
35	262	265	164	190	38.27	0.09	1.23	0.621	31.11
45	278	270	156	190	37.20	0.10	1.26	0.636	29.52
55	305	300	150	182	35.75	0.11	1.29	0.652	27.71
65	324	322	143	180	34.65	0.19	1.55	0.783	22.35
75	348	330	136	176	33.36	0.23	1.70	0.859	19.62
80	370	350	130	170	32.03	0.28	1.90	0.959	16.86
	Pb(NO ₃) ₂ (J)								
20	232	210	192	205	43.10	0.05	1.12	0.566	38.48
35	246	220	184	205	42.16	0.08	1.20	0.606	35.13
45	262	240	180	192	40.39	0.09	1.23	0.621	32.84
55	291	295	171	190	39.13	0.10	1.26	0.636	31.06
65	320	310	160	186	37.39	0.17	1.48	0.748	25.26
75	327	320	160	186	37.39	0.19	1.55	0.783	24.12
80	340	336	158	182	36.77	0.25	1.78	0.899	20.66
	MnSO ₄ (K)								
20	200	200	180	195	40.59	0.04	1.09	0.551	37.24
35	240	240	180	194	40.59	0.08	1.20	0.606	33.82
45	260	260	180	194	40.59	0.09	1.23	0.621	33.00
55	287	280	174	190	39.48	0.09	1.23	0.621	32.09
65	312	300	170	190	39.00	0.15	1.41	0.712	27.66
75	318	300	166	187	38.23	0.18	1.51	0.763	25.32
80	340	330	162	185	37.55	0.25	1.78	0.899	21.09
	NaNO ₃ (L)								
20	270	250	156	187	36.97	0.10	1.26	0.636	29.34
35	280	260	148	180	35.31	0.19	1.54	0.782	22.93
45	288	260	146	180	35.04	0.26	1.82	0.919	19.25
55	322	310	124	172	31.32	0.34	2.19	1.105	14.30
65	336	325	120	168	30.43	0.43	2.69	1.359	11.31
75	365	350	112	166	29.08	0.61	4.07	2.056	7.14
80	391	380	112	166	29.08	0.65	4.47	2.258	6.50
	C.W.								
20	560	520	57	80	14.47	1.65	44.66	22.561	0.32
35	583	540	51	78	13.41	1.71	51.28	25.908	0.26
45	690	660	45	78	12.41	1.74	54.95	27.761	0.23
55	700	660	38	80	11.20	1.78	60.25	30.439	0.18
65	702	690	33	80	10.16	1.81	64.56	32.617	0.16
75	722	700	34	76	10.21	1.85	70.79	35.764	0.14
80	734	705	30	76	9.35	1.86	72.44	36.597	0.13

Results and Discussion

The corrosion rate from weight-loss and potentiostatic measurements have been calculated as reported earlier³. Table 1 shows the results obtained from NACE standard TM-01-69 method for all aqueous salt solutions at various temperatures for 24 h period of immersion. The corrosion of cast iron in various aqueous salt solutions follow the order: A > B > C > G > D > F > E > L > H for 20–80°. But for 20–35° it is H=I > J=K; for 55–65°, H > I > J=K and for 75–80°, H > I > K > J. The weight-loss order, relative increase in the corrosion rate and percentage contribution of each salt show that cast iron is resistive towards NaHCO₃, CaCO₃, CaCl₂ and is corroded to higher extent in NaCl and KCl. In these solutions, corrosion increases due to pitting and hydrogen embrittlement by Cl⁻ ions, whereas in case of CaCO₃ it decreases due to the formation of carbonate layer alongwith the corrosion product⁴. However, for CaCl₂ resistivity is lowered at high temperature. The order for NaCl, KCl, Na₂SO₄, NaHCO₃ and CaCO₃ remains the same at all temperatures because of their high concentrations. On the other hand, MnSO₄ and Pb(NO₃)₂ exhibit no corrosion on account of their low concentration.

Fig. 1 reveals that in Na₂SO₄, CaCO₃, NaHCO₃, MnSO₄, MgSO₄, Pb(NO₃)₂ and NaNO₃ test solutions, corrosion rate gives approximately linear curves with temperature unlike in NaCl, KCl, CaCl₂, KI and KBr test solutions which shows a slight inclination towards y-axis at higher temperatures⁵. The activation energies (E_a), calculated from Arrhenius plots⁶ for cast iron in different test solutions are given in Table 1. E_a value is maximum for MnSO₄ (27.34 kJ mol⁻¹) and minimum for NaCl (21.93 kJ mol⁻¹). E_a values in composite water is 8.68 kJ mol⁻¹.

Fig. 1. Corrosion rate vs temperature curves for cast iron in various test solutions for 24 h period of immersion.

Fig. 2. Potential vs temperature curves for cast iron in various test solutions for 24 h period of immersion.

Potentiostatic polarization behavior : The variations of open-circuit potential (OCP) produced by cast iron in various test solutions are shown in Fig. 2 and anodic and cathodic curves in Fig. 3 at 20°. The anodic and cathodic curves for 35–80° are also recorded. The potentiostatic

Fig. 3. Potentiostatic polarization curves for cast iron in solutions for 24 h period of immersion at 20°.

parameters⁷ calculated from polarization curves are given in Table 2. Tafel slopes, R_p , OCP, E_{corr} decrease whereas corrosion rate and corrosion current increase with the increase in temperature⁸. The effect of temperature is further demonstrated by Tafel relationship in Tafel slopes with increase in temperature, indicating dissolution of anode. The corrosion rates calculated from potentiostatic measurements were found to be higher than that calculated from weight-loss method. The weight-loss method gives the average corrosion rate⁹ over a period of 24 h whereas the electrochemical method represents the instantaneous corrosion rate after 24 h immersion.

Experimental

The grey cast iron square specimens ($2 \times 2 \text{ cm}^2 \times 0.5 \text{ cm}$ thickness) were cast in the die by appropriate casting procedure. The chemical composition of the cast iron used was : C, 3.26; S, 0.10; Si, 2.25; Mn, 0.59; P, 0.06%, besides iron, as analyzed by standard method¹⁰. The specimen surface was smoothed and a hole was drilled near the upper edge. The specimens were cleaned by buffing, degreased in benzene, washed with 50% acetone, dried and weighed to a constant weight before exposing to the corrosive medium¹¹.

Test mediums were prepared by dissolving various salts (A.R.) taken in tolerable concentration for drinking water in distilled water (amount in ppm) : 600 NaCl, 600 KCl, 400 CaCO_3 , 120 CaCl_2 , 150 MgSO_4 , 400 NaHCO_3 , 65 NaNO_3 , 5 MnSO_4 , 3 $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, 5 KBr and 5 KI. To develop an insight in the relative behavior of salts and their contribution to corrosion in water a test solution containing all the above salts was prepared for the study.

Procedure : The specimens were suspended by a glass hook in a beaker filled with test solution at different temperatures (20 to 80°) for 24 h period of immersion. After definite period of exposure, specimens were removed and cleaned as per recommended procedure in a solution of hydrochloric acid, 50 gpl stannous chloride and 20 gpl antimony chloride, dried and weighed.

Experimental setup for polarization measurement consisted of potentiostat/galvanostat (Elico CL-95) with a sweep generator. Saturated calomel electrode was used as reference electrode. The open-circuit potential in the test solution was followed as a function of temperature. Anodic as well as cathodic potentiostatic polarization curves were drawn at a sweep rate of 5 mV/s. All electrochemical studies were made in 500 ml of test solutions¹².

References

1. B. Hammouti, S. Kertit and A. Melhaocci, *Bull. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1995, **11**, 553; F. J. Nagies, B. Kusian and K. E. Heusler, *Proc. Electrochem. Soc. Germany*, 1995, 295.
2. R. Mehra and A. Soni, *J. Indian Council Chem.*, 2001, **18**, 22; *Indian J. Chem. Technol.*, 2001, **9**, 74.
3. R. Mehra and A. Soni, *J. Eng. Mat. Sci.*, 2002, **9**, 141; *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 2002, **61**, 705.
4. D. A. Jones, "Principles and Prevention of Corrosion", 2nd ed., Prentice Hall, Upper Saddle River, 1996; M. Adhikari and K. Choudhury, "Frontiers in Applied Chemistry", Norosa Publishing, New Delhi, 1995; F. M. Kharafat and W. A. Badaway, *Bull. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1998, **14**, 260.
5. F. R. Billman, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1972, 1019, 1198.
6. K. C. Koshel, J. S. Bhatia, K. Shailendra and A. K. Samant, *Bull. Nat. Gas. Common.*, 1988, **25**, 175.
7. R. Francis, *Br. Corros. J.*, 1983, **18**, 35.
8. W. A. Badaway, F. M. Al Kharafi and E. Y. Hassan, *Bull. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1998, **14**, 449; A. K. Singh and N. J. Rao, *Indian J. Chem. Technol.*, 1994, **1**, 225.
9. M. G. Fontana, "Corrosion Engineering", 3rd. ed., McGraw-Hill, London, 1986.
10. A. I. Vogel, "Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longmans Green, London, 1964.
11. R. Mehra and A. Soni, *Bull. Mater. Sci.*, 2002, **25**, 53.
12. A. J. Bard and L. R. Faulkner, "Electrochemical Methods", Wiley, New York, 1980; R. Mehra and A. Soni, *Indian J. Eng. Mat. Sci.*, 2002, **9**, 218.